

FINANCIAL SECTOR EFFICIENCY AND ECONOMIC GROWTH NEXUS IN NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20407428>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of financial sector indicators on economic growth in Nigeria, 1986-2024. The specific objectives were to: examine the effect of credit to private sector, ascertain the effect of interest rate on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. Ex-post facto design was adopted for this study. Annual time series data for 38 years (1986-2024) were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. A preliminary test was conducted using Descriptive Statistics and Augmented Dickey-Fuller to ensure data stationarity. Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) regression technique was used to estimate the variables. Decisions were based on a 5% level of significance. Results showed that credit to private sector had non-significant and positive effect on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria (coeff = 0.046304, pv = 0.4675 > 0.05), interest rate had significant and positive effect on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria (coeff = 0.246753, pv 0.0169 < 0.05). Based on findings, it was recommended that although credit to private sector was found to have non-significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP), maintaining low and stable credit to private sector remains vital. Policymakers should continue implementing effective credit to private sector policies to control investment and prevent potential negative effects on economic growth and despite the significant effect of interest rates on RGDP, interest rate policies should not be ignored.

KEYWORDS

Financial Sector Indicators; Economic Growth; Credit to Private Sector; Interest Rate; Real Gross Domestic Product.

INTRODUCTION

The financial sector of any economy in the world plays a key role in the development and growth of the economy. An efficient financial system is essential for building a sustained economic growth and an open

vibrant economic system. Countries with well developed financial institutions tend to grow faster; especially the size of the banking system and the liquidity of the stock markets tend to have strong positive impact on economic growth (Obianagwa & Eze, 2020).

The evolution of Nigeria's financial sector has been a crucial aspect of the country's growth. In the 1970s, the sector was predominantly controlled by the government, which held significant shares in most banks. The financial crisis of the 1980s led to the introduction of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, aimed at reviving the financial sector through financial liberalization (Jude, Haruna, Mohammed & Richard, 2022). Reforms such as the 2004 consolidation exercise, privatization, commercialization, and recapitalization have since been implemented to strengthen the sector and sustain economic growth (Obianagwa & Eze, 2020; Akintunde & Olaniran, 2022, as cited in Jude et al., 2022).

The financial sector plays a critical role in economic growth and stability by facilitating resource allocation, promoting investment, and fostering innovation. Over the past four decades, from 1981 to 2021, Nigeria's financial sector has undergone significant transformations, including regulatory reforms and technological advancements, enhancing financial intermediation and stability. Financial sector development, measured by the depth, efficiency, and accessibility of financial services, stimulates economic growth by improving credit availability, reducing transaction costs, and facilitating risk management. A well-functioning financial system promotes investment, trade, and efficient resource allocation, contributing to economic growth (Adelakun, 2011, as cited in Sennuga, Adenaike, Adedayo & Sennuga, 2021).

The financial system in any economy that comprises financial institutions with the primary function of effective and efficient provision of savings for investment is very significant for the economic growth of any nation. Hence, the financial system is being noticed as playing an important function in domestic advancement throughout the world (Deema and Buthiena, 2022). The true determinant of advancement in the economy is economic growth, as an increase in “gross domestic product (GDP) is a result of economic growth” (Adeniran and Sidiq, 2023). As opined by Nzotta and Okereke, (2019), economic growth involves an increase in services, output, and jobs to improve the financial well-being of citizens. Financial sector indicators refers to an increase in the economy supply of financial assets through exchange rate, interest rate, inflation rate, market capitalization and broad money supply. Financial sector indicators means that financial institutions will efficiently and effectively make use of, savings for investments as a result of financial intervention by improving the financial markets' competitive efficacy (Jhingan, 2022). Based on this, the study seeks to investigate effect of financial sector indicators on economic growth in Nigeria, 1986-2024.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the financial sector indicators positively influencing credit to private sector, interest rate, stock market capitalization and exchange rate remained negative, averaging -13.5 percent during the reform years, compared to - 7.7 percent during periods of financial repression. High inflation rates, coupled with the re-imposition of interest rate ceilings, contributed to these negative real deposit rates, thereby hindering overall macroeconomic performance. While the reforms have stimulated growth in the Nigerian banking industry, they have not significantly fostered broader development. The banking system remains highly scrutinized, with loans and advances being difficult to obtain, even when strict collateral conditions are met. Unlike banks in developed countries, which encourage the use of loan and credit facilities, Nigerian banks often deter potential customers with stringent requirements. Based on this, the study seeks to investigate effect of financial sector indicators on economic growth in Nigeria, 1986-2024. Therefore, the main objective of the study is to examine the effect of

financial sector indicators on economic growth in Nigeria, 1986-2024. The specific objectives were to;examine the effect of credit to private sector on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria and ascertain the effect of interest rate on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Financial Sector Indicators

Olusegun et al. (2023), it is a rise in a nation's rate of production of goods and services over a specific time period.They clarify that the rise in the volume of goods and services produced in a nation serves as a gauge of economic growth. Jhingan (2023) makes the argument that an economy is regarded to be expanding when it raises the production of more goods and services in relation to this.

Credit to Private Sector

Credit to private sector refers to financial resources provided to the private sector by financial corporations, such as through loans, purchases of non-equity securities, and trade credits and other accounts receivable, that establish a claim for repayment. The financial corporations include monetary authorities and deposit money banks, as well as other financial corporations. Private sector initiative and investment are critical for poverty reduction (Okezie & Enyeribe, 2025).

Interest Rate

Interest rate refers to the rental fee for the borrower's use of credit or the lender's return for giving up liquidity (Amah, 2025). It is the price of money and, like other prices; it tries to perform a rationing role in the market by making it easier to distribute the limited supply of credits among the many competing requests for it. Interest rate is the amount charged by banks when they advance loans to their customers.

Economic Growth

Jhingan (2023), economic growth is defined as a gain in output, and it is correlated with a quantitatively sustained increase in a country's per capita income or output, as well as growth in its labour force, consumption, capital, and volume of trade. The primary indicators of economic growth include high rates of per capita income or production growth, high rates of productivity, rapid structural change, and global movements of capital, products, and labour (Ochejele, 2022).

Theoretical Framework Loanable Fund Theory

This study was anchored on Loanable funds theory. Loanable funds theory advocate that the demand curve for investment funds slopes downward presenting that less funds are borrowed at a higher rates and more at a lower rates of interest. The theory stated that banks cannot always set high interest rates, e.g. trying to earn maximum interest income. If interest rates by banks are fixed too high, it may result to adverse selection challenges because high-risk borrowers are willing to accept these high rates. Once these borrowers receive the loans, they may develop moral hazard attitude or so called borrower moral hazard since they are likely to take on highly risky projects or investments.

Empirical Review

Ogwuche and Obiaje (2023) conducted an analysis on the effect of monetary policy on Nigeria's economic growth from 1985 to 2022. Using the ARDL model, they observed that in the long term, only the interest rate significantly influenced economic growth. Furthermore, while exchange rate, money supply, and interest rate maintained a positive relationship with growth, inflation rate was noted to have a negative association.

Nwagu and Udeagbala (2024) studied effect of bank credit to the private sector on the performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The study investigated the effect of bank credit to the private sector on the

performance of manufacturing sector in Nigeria, from 1981 – 2021. The result of the study revealed that credit to the private sector (CPS), interest rate; and exchange rate.

Eleje, Atadiose and Onwumere (2024) investigated impact of domestic credit on economic performance In Nigeria. This study examined the impact of domestic credit on economic performance in Nigeria from the period 1991-2022. The research was based on ex-post facto research design using a time series data. The study utilized ARDL bound test approach to analyze the result. The findings showed that gross domestic product had positive but non-significant impact on both credit to the private and public sectors in Nigeria.

Oji and Odi (2024) studied sectoral credit allocation and the growth of Nigerian Real Sector. The study employed multiple regression models to estimate the relationship that exists between monetary transmission channels and real sector growth. From model one; the study found 59.2 percent variation in the growth of Nigeria real sector output could be traced to variation in the sectorial credit allocations.

For instance, LawalandRabiu (2024) investigated the impact of monetary policy and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022. The results shown that monetary policy rate, lagged values of interest rate and money supply positively impacted the growth of the economy. In a related study, Innocent et al (2024), examined the relationship between monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria when there is evidence of structural break. The findings shown that while Money Supply (M2) has a significant positive impact on economic growth in the short run, net credit to Government (NCG) has a negative significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria. This study concludes that broad money supply contributed to economic growth in the short run.

Using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and ex-post facto research methodology Ugwu Flora Onyinye (2024) explored the impact of monetary policy on the economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 and 2017. The result indicated that interest rates had significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth, while monetary policy rate and exchange rate have negative relationship with economic growth in Nigeria.

Gaps in Empirical Review

There is gap in data as many studies could not extend to 2024. This present study used the most recent available data by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) through their statistical bulletin thereby revealing the current situation between financial sector indicators and economic growth variables. There was gap in the model used. Some used ECM, VEM etc but we are going to use Ordinary Least Square Method (OLS) model. There are also gap in area of study for many are foreign authors but few are Nigerians. And also gap in the objectives of the study for many authors used different financial sectors indicators such as credit to private sector and interest rate as control variables over economic.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design/Nature and Sources of Data

This study adopted the *ex post*-factor research design. The *ex post*facto research design is described as after-the-fact research using time series data (Onwumere, 2012).The nature and sources of data for this research was secondary data sources. The secondary data source is through the Annual Reports and Accounts of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) under consideration in the research.

Model Specification

This work used simple regression model. It follows the model was used byObuduisine and Olowolaju, (2014) in their work titled impact of macroeconomic variables on the economylesson from Nigeria using Ordinary Least Square Regression Method. Hence, this direct model was used as thus;

$RGDP = F(\text{TOPN}, \text{EXTRSV} \text{ and } M2)$,

Where, TOPN= Trade openness, EXTRSV= External reserve and M2 = money supply from banks as a measures of macroeconomic activities.

This study was deviated from the use of credit to private sector, interest rate, stock market capitalization and exchange rate, thus:

$RGDP = F(\text{CPS}, \text{INTR})$,

Where,

CPS = Credit to Private Sector

INTR = Interest Rate

Hence, this study was anchored on the above model used by Obuduisine and Olowolaju, (2014) by modifying it to accommodate credit to private sector and interest rate. Also, a special type of model that superior to Ordinary Least Square called simple regression model was used for this study

The mathematical expression for this model is written thus

$$RGDP_t = B_0 + B_1 CPS_t + B_2 INTR_t + \beta_n X_{nt-n} + E_t: \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

CPS = Credit to Private Sector

INTR = Interest Rate

E_t = Error term

B_0 = Coefficient of Equilibrium. Or Center of origin

$\beta_1, \dots\dots\dots \beta_2$ = Proxies of the Coefficient of the parameter estimates.

t = Time series data.

$t-1, t-2$ = Lag values of the variables

Disaggregation the Model Based on Hypotheses.

Model 1 = Hypothesis One

Credit to private sector has no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

$$RGDP_t = B_0 + B_1 CPS_t + E_t: \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product

CPS = Credit to Private Sector

Model 2 = Hypothesis Two

Interest rate has no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

$$RGDP_t = B_0 + B_1 INTR_t + E_t: \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where: RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product

INTR = Interest Rate

Techniques of Analyses

The study used simple regression analysis method (OLS). However, it incorporate bound testing co-integration test in order to undertake a thorough examination of the characteristics of time series economic data. The analytical procedures involved are; first, unit root test was carried out for each of the variables so as to ascertain the time series properties of the data set and obtain the stationary status. Unit root test or stationary test was a preliminary test that was done to prevent running a spurious regression.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Descriptive Statistics

Here, the statistical and econometric characteristics of the study variables were explained. Particularly, statistics such as mean and standard deviations, skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera test for normality were reported.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics Result

	RGDP	IR	CPS
Mean	56213.06	18.30692	10618.61
Median	22884.90	17.95000	1838.390
Maximum	234425.9	29.80000	52884.78
Minimum	196.1700	10.50000	15.25000
Std. Dev.	69481.61	3.782577	14658.11
Skewness	1.241027	0.813909	1.503834
Kurtosis	3.474092	4.644080	4.520648
Jarque-Bera	10.37620	8.698286	18.45746
Probability	0.005583	0.012918	0.000098
Observations	39	39	39

Source: Researcher’s Computation Using Eviews 10.0

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of our data set, and shows that, on the average, RGDP was 5.62%, RER averaged at 136.33%, MCAP was on average of 12.82%, IR stood at average of 18.31%, CPS average was 10.61% respectively. In addition, the results shows that the data series of our response variable are positively skewed, has no excess kurtosis and follows normal distribution; hence, statistically different from zero. The data series of variables are positively skewed ($Sk > 0$) while IR is negatively skewed ($SK < 0$). There is excess kurtosis ($K > 3.0$) in series of IR among all the independent variables. Therefore, only the series of IR did not follow normal distribution. The rest independent variables have their kurtosis less than or not significantly above 3.0; hence, they are confirmed to follow normal distribution.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Credit to private sector has no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Credit to private sector has positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis (H₀) if p-value of the t-statistic is less than 0.05; otherwise, do not reject the null hypothesis.

Table 4.2 ARDL Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOGRGDP(-1)	1.208536	0.168307	7.180557	0.0000
LOGRGDP(-2)	-0.287974	0.166706	-1.727433	0.0934
LOGCPS	0.046304	0.062997	0.735013	0.4675

C	0.538154	0.224471	2.397431	0.0223
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R-squared	0.998160	Mean dependent var		9.758930
Adjusted R-squared	0.997993	S.D. dependent var		2.020610
S.E. of regression	0.090533	Akaike info criterion		-1.864392
Sum squared resid	0.270477	Schwarz criterion		-1.690238
Log likelihood	38.49125	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.802994
F-statistic	5966.636	Durbin-Watson stat		1.993641
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

The result of the ARDL model presented in Table 4.2 shows that the regression coefficient of CPS is -0.046304 with a T-statistic equal to 0.735013. Since the t-statistic is greater than 2.0 in absolute terms, the result is statistically none significant at the 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis one under consideration is rejected. The conclusion is that credit to private sector has a non significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₂: Interest rate has no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Ha₂: Interest rate has positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject the null hypothesis (Ho) if p-value of the t-statistic is less than 0.05; otherwise, do not reject the null hypothesis.

Table 4.3 ARDL Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOGRGDP(-1)	1.088681	0.171701	6.340558	0.0000
LOGRGDP(-2)	0.008937	0.266305	0.033559	0.9735
LOGRGDP(-3)	-0.480343	0.253927	-1.891653	0.0702
LOGRGDP(-4)	0.373544	0.158405	2.358155	0.0265
LOGIR	0.246753	0.096411	2.559380	0.0169
LOGIR(-1)	-0.018189	0.107009	-0.169978	0.8664
LOGIR(-2)	-0.032524	0.090543	-0.359210	0.7225
LOGIR(-3)	0.323060	0.088444	3.652695	0.0012
LOGIR(-4)	0.140033	0.079982	1.750800	0.0922
C	-1.605874	0.738857	-2.173457	0.0394
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R-squared	0.998825	Mean dependent var		9.980508
Adjusted R-squared	0.998402	S.D. dependent var		1.840362
S.E. of regression	0.073572	Akaike info criterion		-2.146156

Sum squared resid	0.135320	Schwarz criterion	-1.701771
Log likelihood	47.55773	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.992754
F-statistic	2361.078	Durbin-Watson stat	2.168955
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

The result of the ARDL model presented in Table 4.3 shows that the regression coefficient of IR is -0.246753 with a T-statistic equal to 2.559380. Since the t-statistic is greater than 2.0 in absolute terms, the result is statistically significant at the 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis two under consideration is rejected. The conclusion is that interest rate has a significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Credit to private sector has no positive and significant real effect on gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Therefore, the null hypothesis one under consideration is rejected. The conclusion is that credit to private sector has a non significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. This is inconsistent with study of Okorie and Chikwendu (2019) examined does private sector credit impact on private sector investment in Nigeria. This study therefore examines the extent to which private sector credit impacts on private sector investment in Nigeria. The ARDL model was engaged in data analysis. From the analysis, the following results were established, that private sector credit has positive and significant impact on private sector investment in the short run, but in the long run, private sector credit has positive and insignificant impact on private sector investment in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: Interest rate has no positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Therefore, the null hypothesis two under consideration is rejected. The conclusion is that interest rate has a significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. Similarly it was agreed with evidence of study by Ayodeji and Oluwole (2018) analyzed the impact of various monetary policy instruments, including Money Supply (MS), Exchange Rate (ER), Interest Rate (IR), and Liquidity Ratio (LR), on economic growth from 1981 to 2016 using VECM. They found that the money supply and exchange rate had a positive but limited effect, whereas interest rate and liquidity ratio had a significant negative effect on economic growth. Findings suggested that interest rates had a modest effect on growth. Henry and Sabo (2020) Their ARDL analysis demonstrated that while the monetary policy rate and exchange rate negatively influenced inflation, broad money supply positively impacted it.

Summary of Findings

i. Credit to private sector had non significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria (coeff = 0.046304, $p_v = 0.4675 > 0.05$). This implies that every 1% change in credit to private sector attract 46% increase in real domestic product in Nigeria.

ii. Interest rate had significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria (coeff = 0.246753, $p_v 0.0169 < 0.05$). This implies that every 1% change in interest rate attract 25% increase real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria.

Conclusion

In the light of summary of findings, the study concluded that financial sector indicators had significant positive effect on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria. But specifically variables also concluded that credit to private sector had non significant and positive effect on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria, interest rate had significant and positive effect on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Although credit to private sector was found to had non significant and positive effect on real gross domestic product (RGDP), maintaining low and stable credit to private sector remains vital. Policymakers should continue implementing effective credit to private sector policies to control investment and prevent potential negative effects on economic growth.
- ii. Despite the significant effect of interest rates on RGDP, interest rate policies should not be ignored. Policymakers should explore macroeconomic conditions under which interest rate adjustments could have a more significant effect on growth. Creating an enabling economic environment can enhance the effectiveness of interest rate adjustments in stimulating economic activity.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study's significance lies in its contribution to the existing body of knowledge, providing empirical validation of the adverse consequences associated with financial sector indicators in the Nigerian context. By illuminating the adverse effects of financial sector indicators, the study serves as a catalyst for informed policy decisions and strategic interventions aimed at safeguarding Nigeria's economic stability and fostering economic growth.

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